

Assessment of the active data management ecosystem at Western Sydney University

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

Western Sydney University

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

Western Sydney University (WSU) has engaged our Cloud Services provider Intersect to provide access to Mediaflux on an Intersect research data management platform called Idea. Idea has been designed with the intention of managing research data throughout the full data lifecycle from collection to archiving. WSU research data is currently stored across many different silos and although some thought has gone into management of data through research data management plans, the use of metadata is not consistent and often nonexistent.

Our approach in implementation of the Active Data Management element of the Framework was to take the turnkey Mediaflux platform, configure using default metadata schema and engage with researchers in ingesting live research project datasets. A key consideration was to have researchers involved at all stages of Active Data Management solution planning process (User-Focused Design) and foster compliance by design to reduce the burden of managing working data at scale.

A small number of datasets were onboarded to the new system during the training phase of implementing Mediaflux as a working data storage solution. This involved provisioning of data collections in Mediaflux, data cleaning and standardising file naming conventions for datasets. With this came the need to understand the roles and responsibilities related to research data management and the complementary research data governance framework. The WSU Research Data Management Policy provides some guidance on who has the responsibility to make decisions about active(working) data and its management but falls short of establishing such a framework.

WSU is currently developing a Data Classification and Handling Guide to define a framework for assessing the sensitivity of data in electronic systems, apply a classification with minimum handling requirements needed to protect the University's data, and is applied to all data that are created, collected, stored or processed by the university, in electronic formats. This guide defines the key roles of Data Custodian (responsible for the business use of the data), Data Owner (with administrative and/or operational responsibility for data), and Data User (An individual who has been granted explicit authorisation by the relevant Data Owner to access, use, alter or destroy data within an information system). These data handling roles were then mapped to the Mediaflux data management access roles of system administrator, project leader and researcher, respectively.

Implementation of the Active Data Management element of [the Framework](#) also considered the importance of metadata when it comes to research datasets. Metadata (those elements which describe the research data) allows discoverability, interoperability and reusability of research data and is therefore a key consideration to any institution's successful adoption of a research data framework and platform. The identification of a set of key metadata about data that supports good management and automation, determination of the points where this metadata will be collected, and a common source of truth for this metadata.

The need for a well-integrated research data management system was also considered especially for providing a seamless user experience. Researchers should 'know what they know', be aware of what's captured in their own research datasets and where they are stored in physical and digital form. After completing a research project, this information may be documented to a lower level or not documented at all, making research data difficult to find, access and reuse. This poses challenges for other researchers when it comes to reproducibility and furthering future research.

WSU currently uses ReDBox from Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF) to collect research data management plans (RDMP) from researchers. This RDMP tool details how the data will be managed, analysed and stored, as well as what mechanisms may be in place for licensing and preservation. Investigation of ReDBox and MediaFlux found that whilst there were some shared metadata attributes, there were other attributes used in both systems that did not have equivalents. Since the MediaFlux asset structure features a complex series of nested nodes whereas the RDMP tool captures metadata at the project level, this was not unexpected.

Mediaflux and its collection-based system of storing active research data also offers the potential for automation of data collection through interfacing with analytical instruments that produce both raw and processed datasets. WSU has embarked on a Proof of Concept with Intersect to validate a data movement tool called DataBolt. DataBolt will provide an automated process to move raw data from the data acquisition computer of an instrument to a defined collection in Mediaflux. Work is progressing on building the required local data collection agents to be installed on instrument computers, configuration of remote data agents to deliver the data to Mediaflux and design of a consistent and informative file system structure.

Resulting Improvements

We have established a unique working relationship between Research Services, the IT division and the Library led by a solutions-focused working group. Data flows from research projects, through IT systems and ends up managed by the Library. Thus, there is a natural involvement in active data management from these three key support areas in our university.

We have gained valuable insights into the update of WSU Research Data Management Policy with key aspects of the Active Data Management element incorporated into the Policy.

We have also focused on the roles and responsibilities for institutional data governance. The key data management roles identified include: data owner, data custodian, and data user. Cross matching of roles across research data management policy and associated guidelines and procedures is underway.

We have also developed an early model for a fit for purpose metadata schema based on common standards. The Idea Mediaflux platform has a metadata schema embedded in the data handling pipeline. The default schema is based on Dublin Core. We now see a need to consider the metadata schema requirements for our REDbox dataset collection submission and a cross walk to the Mediaflux platform.

A single metadata standard across universities would need to define the minimum level of metadata necessary for optimum impact. If adopted, this metadata schema could be applied across the research data continuum, from creation of research data management plan through to data publication.

Next Steps

1. Onboarding researchers with live datasets has been a slow process. With Idea being run as a pilot we have looked for data champions as there is no guarantee that the data collections once established in the platform would be taken up by research teams.
2. Moving to a collection-based system for managing active data is certainly a step change for most researchers and we are working on promoting a set of use cases across STEM, HASS and Health disciplines that fit the data management ecosystem at WSU.
3. Investigation of ways in which metadata from the RDMP tool could map to that in MediaFlux, as well as be harvested bi-directionally, so that the RDMP and the data storage would always be synchronised; also discussing the possibility of adding an RDMP tool to MediaFlux, as that way the plan and the data could be held in the same place.

Project Outputs

Reusable outputs produced include:

“Towards a Step Change in Managing Research Data at Western Sydney University”

<https://doi.org/10.26183/4atv-3s04>

A summary report of WSU’s pilot implementation of MediaFlux with specific focus on:

- The approach taken to try to include researchers in the design phase of the system, and a general assessment of how successful and effective this proves to be (User-Focused Design).
- An assessment of the usefulness (and hence level of incentive) of MediaFlux and associated utilities to participating researchers in moving data in and/or out of their working storage, and also organisation of their data while located on working storage. (Compliance by Design).
- An assessment of the pilot platform against the Platform Selection criteria from the Active Data management element
- Researchers’ understanding of who has the responsibility to make decisions about data and its management (Research Data Governance).

“Metadata: A Case Study at Western Sydney University”

<https://doi.org/10.26183/t8x5-hf62>

A report written as a “case study” of the work done around metadata within the pilot to:

- Develop an initial top-level research data metadata schema.
- Assess how effective and appropriate this schema proves to be as a number of real-life research datasets are onboarded.
- Summarise learnings from this process together with several key recommendations around research data metadata and associated schema design (Integration for a Seamless User Experience).

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).